

Original Research

Private Sector Challenges in Sustainable Solid Waste Management, Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania

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Abstract

This qualitative study investigates the challenges and opportunities surrounding sustainable solid waste management (SWM) practices within Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. Drawing upon participation theory, which emphasizes context, design, power, and scale fit, the study's primary objective is to analyze the challenges private entities face in effectively implementing sustainable SWM practices. In-depth interviews, focused group discussions and direct observation data collection methods were applied to collect data. The study used thematic data analysis to examine the research problem. The study findings revealed challenges like inefficiencies in decision-making processes, limited emphasis on sustainability, and poor contracts which do not pave the way to sustainable solid waste management practices. On the opportunity side, findings revealed that the private sector is willing to invest in modern technologies and establish links with other economic sectors, indicating potential paths for sustainable solid waste management. These findings contribute to the body of knowledge by highlighting the importance of inclusive decision-making processes and collaborative approaches in enhancing SWM practices. This study suggests that the Dar es Salaam Municipal Waste Management Department should establish a synergistic relationship between private-sector engagement and innovations in waste separation, reuse, recycling and recovery practices.

Keywords: Private Entity, Sustainability, Waste Management.

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Introduction

Background Information

Efficient waste management is an increasingly critical concern in urban areas worldwide, given the daily generation of millions of tons of solid waste, which poses significant environmental challenges (De, Ferrara, Iannone, & Parente, 2019). The generated Solid Waste (SW) needs to be managed sustainably in a manner that it does not become harmful to human health and to the environment; otherwise, it is a breeding ground for disease outbreaks, it can lead to ecological degradation, soil and water contamination, and contribute to global warming (Darmey, Ahiekpor, Narra, & Achaw, 2023). Consequently, promoting sustainable management of SW has become a paramount global concern with much emphasis on the collaboration between the government and the private sectors (Abubakar, et al., 2022). The focus on incorporating the private sector in SWM for sustainable results was publicised in principle number 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development adopted in September 1992 (United Nations, 2008).

Sustainable waste management goes beyond traditional practices of collection, transportation, and disposal, instead, it views waste as a valuable resource. This approach involves segregating waste at its source, reusing, recycling, or recovery before its final disposal (Perkumienė, Atalay, Safaa, & Grigienė, 2023). Waste separation involves sorting reusable waste, while waste reuse entails extracting value from discarded items that can still be usable. Recycling involves processing used, reused, or unused items into raw materials and manufacturing new products (Perkumienė, Atalay, Safaa, & Grigienė, 2023). The ultimate goal of sustainable SWM is to ensure that the maximum value of waste is extracted before it is disposed of. This entails sorting out or separating solid waste which can still be reused or recycled from the waste which can no longer be used again or recycled, then the useful sorted waste can be used in the manufacturing and industrial sector to produce new materials and products instead of extracting new raw materials from nature. Generally, this requires full awareness and the participation of both the public and the private sector, and policy formation to support waste reuse and recycling.

In recent years, the rapid urbanisation and population growth in cities like Dar es Salaam have intensified the challenges associated with solid waste management (SWM). As urban populations increase, so does the volume of waste generated, placing massive strain on existing waste management infrastructure and systems (Mapunda, Kimwaga, & Kaswi, 2023). The inadequacy of traditional waste management practices to cope with the increasing volume of SW has stressed the need for innovative and sustainable approaches (Nyampundu, Mwegoha, & Millanzi, 2020). Moreover, the socio-economic disparities within urban centres often result in unequal access to waste management services, disproportionately affecting marginalised communities. Addressing these disparities requires an all-inclusive approach that focuses on efficient waste collection, and disposal by the public sector and emphasises the private sector engagement and empowerment.

Furthermore, the globalisation trend has reshaped consumption patterns, leading to increased production of packaging materials, and other disposable items (Wang, Changhong, & Xiaofei, 2022). The disposition of these materials presents significant environmental and health risks if not managed properly. Consequently, there is a growing recognition of the need for a paradigm shift in waste management practices, from a linear model of consumption and disposal to a circular economy approach that emphasises resource efficiency, waste reduction, and material recovery (Ansari, Dharm Dutt, & Vivek, 2024). Embracing circular economy principles offers a promising pathway towards achieving sustainable solid waste management by promoting the reuse, recycling, and recovery of materials, thereby minimising the environmental footprint of waste disposal activities.

To attain sustainable SWM, different cities in the world Dar es Salaam inclusive, have integrated government bodies and non-governmental partners like the private sector that contribute to reducing the financial, technological, and human resource burdens on local government authorities (Albostan & Sharifli, 2023; Gelan, 2021). In Dar es Salaam City, local government authorities at the municipal and ward level have contracted the private sector in terms of private companies and informal groups to manage SW; however, challenges associated with the management of SW continue to persist (University of Dar es Salaam, 2020). This calls for an academic inquiry that focuses on the challenges the private sector face, and the opportunities for promoting sustainable SWM.

Problem Statement

Dar es Salaam City generates the highest amount of Solid Waste than all other Metropolitan Cities in the Country. It generates 4,161 tons of SW per day compared to Mwanza, Mbeya and Arusha which produce 338, 400, and 550 tons of SW per day respectively (Singh, 2021). To reduce the burden of SWM and to ensure sustainable SWM, Dar es Salaam City joined forces with the private sector by contracting private companies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and community-based groups to manage solid waste services. Moreover, according to the Tanzania National Strategy for Solid Waste Management, the public sector in Dar es Salaam and other cities in the country are expected to support the private sector in establishing solid waste recycling systems, to reduce non-biodegradable waste materials like metal, glass, plastic bottles, and used tires (United Republic of Tanzania - URT, 2018; Singh, 2021).

Despite the strategy of contracting the private sector, Dar es Salaam City continues to face challenges related to unsustainable waste management practices. This is evidenced by the available statistics which indicate that less than 50% of the daily 4,161 tons of solid waste is collected, resulting in burning, uncontrolled dumping of the uncollected SW leading to water pollution, odour, and flooding during rain seasons (Mushi, Banele, & Mollel, 2022; Mapunda, Joseph, & Kasuwi, 2023). These challenges are compounded by the limited recognition of waste as a valuable resource (Kihila, Wernsted, & Kaseva, 2021) and are likely to continue if immediate actions are not taken.

Additionally, although prior studies on SWM in Dar es Salaam City have explored challenges faced by municipal authorities and the private sector (Kirama and Mayo, 2016; Kamugisha, 2019; Kihila, 2021; Mnguu, 2021), the focus has been on waste collection,

transportation and disposal. Thus, a gap remains on the challenges that the private sector contracted to manage SW in Dar es Salaam City face, specifically on separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery practices; a further gap exists on the potential opportunities for the local government authorities to manage SW sustainably by using the private sector. This study attempts to cover that gap and enable the respective Dar es Salaam Municipal authorities in collaboration with the private sector to take necessary action in promoting sustainable SWM.

Research Objectives

Generally, this study investigated challenges and opportunities the contracted private sector faces in the sustainable management of Solid Waste in Dar es Salaam City.

Specifically, this study aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. To analyse the challenges the private sector encounters in managing solid waste sustainably in Dar es Salaam City.
2. To explore the opportunities that arise by contracting the private sector in promoting sustainable waste management in Dar es Salaam City.

The Rationale of the Study

The findings of this study will contribute in shading light to the Dar es Salaam City Authority on the challenges that hinder the sustainable management of SW, and eventually identify prospects for promoting a more sustainable approach to waste management as a result of private sector integration.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

This sub-section analyses the theory of Participation in Sustainable Waste Management and its relevance to this study.

Theory of Participation in Sustainable Waste Management

Reed, et al. (2018) introduced a new theory of participation that explains the factors contributing to positive environmental and social outcomes through various stakeholder and public engagement efforts. This theory encompasses four key elements: context, design, power, and scale fit. These elements collectively clarify the conditions under which different engagement approaches yield positive results, particularly in Solid Waste Management (SWM). In the context of SWM, stakeholders must align with the unique characteristics of each community since the socio-cultural aspects, economic conditions, and social dynamics of the area play a vital role in determining the most suitable engagement approach.

Within the design element, the theory emphasises the significance of engagement processes that transparently represent the interests of relevant stakeholders. This

engagement process results in a broader range of information and facilitates knowledge exchange. The design element underscores the need for engagements to be mutually beneficial for both governmental bodies and non-governmental entities. By ensuring transparency and inclusivity, well-designed strategies lead to informed decision-making and contribute to positive environmental outcomes. The theory also emphasises the need for power dynamics that acknowledge the value of each participant's input and provide equal opportunities for contribution. Through this, engaging the private sector in SWM becomes more democratic and enables diverse perspectives to shape sustainable waste management strategies.

The scale fit component highlights the need for stakeholders and public involvement to be planned and carried out at spatial scales relevant to the particular problem at hand and line up with the domain of the contracting authorities. This element acknowledges that different issues require varying durations to achieve the desired outcomes. Some may require extended periods for tangible results, while others could yield quicker results

The applicability of the participation theory in this study broadens the understanding of how the engagement of stakeholders, including both the private sector and governmental bodies, can promote the desired outcomes and sustainability in SWM. Thus, the theoretical framework that guided the study drew upon several key concepts, including context, design, power, and scale fit, which serve as analytical lenses for examining the complexities of solid waste management in the context of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

Specifically, context is employed to explore the challenges faced by stakeholders operating within the dynamic environment of Dar es Salaam, considering its status as the densely populated commercial hub of the country. The design was used as a guiding principle revealing how collaboration between the public and the private sectors' approaches can be connected to unlock waste separation, reuse, and recycling practices. Likewise, the power dynamics involved an interplay of interests between the public represented by the wards and the private sector (the contracted companies and informal groups) in shaping sustainable solid waste management practices. Finally, the scale fit informs the examination of how solid waste management strategies are formulated and implemented offering insights into the appropriateness of existing approaches. Generally, these key concepts guided in clarifying the challenges and opportunities arising as the private sector addresses waste management issues related to sorting, reuse and recycling or recovery.

Empirical Literature Review

This section presents findings from studies conducted in different contexts on stakeholders' engagement in sustainable waste management. The aim is to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of waste management practices.

Stakeholders' Participation in Solid Waste Management

The participation of different stakeholders in SWM has been adopted in different cities of the world as an alternative strategy to solve environmental challenges associated with

the increasing generation of SW such as water and air pollution, land degradation, emissions of methane and climate change (Ismaila, et al., 2022). The study by Muiyiwa, Ridwan, and Hans-Rudolf (2023) indicated that in sub-Saharan Africa the annual volume waste increased from 81 million tons in 2012, to 174 tons in 2016 and is projected to reach 269 tons by 2030. Such an increase in the volume of SW generation has necessitated many countries to incorporate the private sector in managing SW due to governments' financial and technical constraints (Afful, et al., 2023). The incorporation of private stakeholders is adopted as a global strategy to attain sustainable SWM. The same is emphasised in principle number 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development adopted in September 1992 (United Nations, 2008).

Despite adopting the strategy of integrating stakeholders, developing countries have continued to experience challenges in SWM. For example, the study by Muiyiwa, Ridwan, and Hans-Rudolf (2023) revealed that in sub-Saharan Africa only 67% of the generated SW was collected in 2018. This implies the existence of challenges that obstruct stakeholders from effectively collecting SW to 100%. Thus, challenges that private stakeholders face in providing SWM need to be uncovered in different localities of developing countries so that more effective strategies to attain sustainable waste management practices are unveiled by respective local authorities.

Another study was conducted by Prince, Ted, and Dzidzo (2020) who assessed the participation of different stakeholders in SWM in Ga West Municipality, Accra-Ghana. The study revealed a limited involvement of stakeholders in sustainable practices of SWM, although there were existing opportunities for composting and recycling. The study recommended the need for public education on solid waste collection, reduction, reuse, recovery and recycling. The benefits of contracting the private sector are uncovered by Mnguu and Eliamani (2021) who examined the performance of outsourcing strategies on SWM in Dodoma City, Tanzania. The study revealed that SWM services in Dodoma City have improved after the decision to outsource SWM service providers. The improvement is based on increased coverage area for SWM services by the private sector has eventually reduced the government burden on transportation costs. However, the study's scope rarely indicated how SWM services improved waste separation or sorting at source, reuse, recycling and recovery practices by both the public and the private sectors.

The study by Muturi (2021) examined the influence of stakeholders' participation and the management of SW disposal. It further identified the main stakeholders of SWM to include local and central government authorities, households, private contractors and ministries of health. Nevertheless, the study did not establish the influence of these stakeholders on SWM. Moreover, Farrah and Ng'ang'a (2022) investigated the relationship between stakeholders' involvement and effective waste management in Mombasa County, Kenya. The study pointed out that Solid waste management is significantly associated with the stakeholders' awareness, commitment and capacity building on issues related to waste management. Generally, the findings of the study played an important role in informing the importance of involving stakeholders if effective solid waste management is to be attained, however, the emphasis of the study was on separation, reuse and recycling remained very minimal.

Another study was conducted by Koiwanit and Filimonau (2023) to explore the issues of stakeholders' participation in SWM in Koh Phayam Island, Thailand. The study revealed that a lack of clear understanding of the benefits that stakeholders accrue by participating in SWM is one of the reasons that most stakeholders do not participate in SWM. The study recommends the establishment of clear financial incentives for stakeholders' participation in SW separation and recycling. This implies that incentives are important motives to make stakeholders participate in SWM.

Challenges Stakeholders Face in Managing Solid Waste

Several studies have been conducted that focus on the challenges that stakeholders in SWM face. Kirama and Mayo (2016) evaluated the effectiveness of involving the private sector in SW collection and transportation and interviewed 20 private service providers. In identifying challenges, the study revealed that the private sector service providers are obstructed by inferior waste collection and transportation equipment, short contract durations and inefficient fee collection systems for SWM services. Additionally, the study proposed that improving waste management services requires raising awareness of willingness to pay for the service and discouraging illegal dumping by community members. Despite revealing challenges, the study rarely focused on waste separation, reuse, recycling and recovery practices.

Another study by Kamugisha, Ludete, and Mhanga (2019) examined factors that influence the performance of Public-Private Partnerships in SWM at Kinondoni Municipality, Dar es Salaam – Tanzania. The study findings revealed that most of the contracted companies had low financial and technical capacities, and there was also a challenge of poor accessibility to residential areas where services are to be provided. Additionally, there was a weak enforcement of waste management laws and regulations. All these challenges obstruct effective SWM practices. Nevertheless, the study focused on waste collection, transportation and disposal.

The study by Nayono and Nayono (2021) aimed to map the challenges stakeholders in SWM face in Nglanggeran. The study identified challenges such as the lack of a formal waste management system in the area and the absence of connections between the existing solid waste infrastructure. Saleh and Marzuki (2023) conducted a study to assess various challenges private companies face in SWM in Kano Metropolis, Nigeria. Among the issues pointed out by the study is that the state government has been directly involved in SWM in a way that it is seen as a competitor of the private sector rather than a compliment. In addition, the scope of private companies is limited to residential areas.

Generally, most of the studies reviewed such as Reed, et al. (2017); Kirama and Mayo (2016); Mnguu and Eliamani, (2021); Farrah and Ng'ang'a (2022); De, Ferrara, Iannone, and Parente (2019), have explored the broader landscape of integration of stakeholders in SWM, and the challenges they experience during their operations. Findings show the overall focus has been on collection, transportation and disposal with limited attention on examining the unique challenges that contracted private sector entities encounter when striving for sustainable waste management practices and potential opportunities associated with their participation in promoting waste separation, reuse, and recycling/recovery, particularly within the setting of Dar es Salaam City. To cover the

gap, this research aims to address this critical gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and opportunities associated with private sector involvement in sustainable SWM. This study focused on waste separation or sorting, reuse, recycling and recovery in context-specific insights and recommendations for achieving long-term, environmentally responsible SWM practices in Dar es Salaam City.

The Conceptual Framework

This study's conceptual framework is informed by the participation theory proposed by Reed et al. (2018), knowledge obtained from the reviewed literature and the researchers' expertise in sustainable solid waste management (SWM). The framework integrates three core elements from the participatory theory: design, power, and scale fit. The design and power aspects of the participation theory are utilized to explore the challenges faced by the private sector and identify opportunities for enhancing SW separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery. This involves examining the extent of private sector engagement in SWM decision-making processes and the transparency of partnerships. The goal is to empower private companies, community-based organizations, and NGOs to play a significant role in sustainable waste management. The framework seeks to balance power dynamics, ensuring that the voices, interests, and expertise of all stakeholders are heard and considered.

The scale fit element is applied to analyze the appropriateness of current SWM approaches in addressing the volume and types of waste generated, as well as the socio-economic context of the locality. This involves assessing whether existing strategies effectively promote sustainable practices such as waste separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery. The framework posits that when the private sector effectively participates in the decision-making process and its interest is accommodated, it is possible to attain sustainable SWM (Dangi & Jamal, 2016).

Research Methods

Selection of the Study Area

Dar es Salaam City is positioned along the Western Coast of the Indian Ocean between 6 and 7 South of the Equator and longitudinally between 33 and 39 East of Greenwich. The city shares its borders with the Coast Region in the North, West, and South, while to the East lies the Indian Ocean. It is characterised by a consistently hot and humid climate while maintaining an average air temperature of 26°C throughout the year (URT, 2023). Dar es Salaam City was chosen as the study area due to its high waste generation rates of 4,161 tons of SW per day which is a significantly big amount in terms of quantity compared to other Tanzanian cities like Arusha, Mwanza, Mbeya, and Dodoma (Singh, 2021). It also has a significant private sector involvement in waste management activities.

Five wards were purposively selected within the city based on the following criteria: Manzese and Tandale: Low-income areas with a higher prevalence of waste management challenges and substantial waste generation. Msasani: A high-income area characterised by planned settlement patterns. Sinza: A medium-income area with notable waste management challenges. Mbezi: A diverse-income area with high levels of waste

generation. The selection of wards was informed by previous studies (Mhache, 2012; Tanzania population census, 2022; and Mapunda, Joseph, and Kasuwi, 2023), which provided insights into the socio-economic characteristics and waste management dynamics of these areas.

Research Approach

This study adopted a qualitative research approach to explore the challenges and opportunities the contracted private sector faces in achieving sustainable solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City. Qualitative methods allowed for an in-depth exploration of stakeholders' perspectives, experiences, and perceptions of waste management. Through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, this approach sought to uncover the underlying challenges affecting the current waste management strategies and identify potential areas for improvement. By focusing on qualitative data collection and analysis, the study aimed to generate rich, contextually relevant insights that can inform policy and decision-making processes to enhance the sustainability of solid waste management practices in the city.

Types of Research Data

Qualitative data was gathered through in-depth interviews, direct observation, and focus group discussions with key stakeholders involved in solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City. This data provided insights into stakeholders' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to the challenges and opportunities of sustainable waste management practices. Open-ended questions were used to explore the sustainable aspects of waste management including waste separation, reuse, and recycling allowing for a deeper understanding of the issues at hand.

Research Data Sources

The key data sources included key stakeholders involved in solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City. These were the representatives from the contracted private sector entities, local government authorities, and informal groups contracted for waste management activities. Secondary data sources were reports from government local authorities, and waste management service providers. These documents included waste management policies, regulations, annual reports, and statistical data on waste generation and disposal in Dar es Salaam City. In addition, direct observations of waste management practices in Dar es Salaam City provided valuable firsthand data on the operational realities of waste management processes. This observational data was used to complement and validate information obtained from interviews, and secondary sources.

Technique for Determining Respondents

Purposive sampling was employed to select participants for this study. The sample comprised 7 private companies and 9 informal groups, totalling 16 entities. The selection of 16 entities aligns with the principle of data saturation, ensuring that data collection continued until no new information emerged. Participants of the study purposively

targeted company managers, truck/wheel carts drivers and companies/informal groups ‘workers who were conveniently available and willing to participate in the study.

The selection criteria for the private companies and informal groups were based on their involvement in solid waste management (SWM) activities within Dar es Salaam City. Specifically, private companies and informal groups were chosen based on their formal contracts at ward levels in waste management services in their respective wards.

In total, 36 individuals were interviewed across the 16 entities. The breakdown of the sample size is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Breakdown of the Sample Size

S/N	Name of the Ward	Sampled Private Companies	Sampled Informal Groups	Participants Interviewed from Private Companies	Participants Interviewed in the Informal Groups
1	Manzese	1	3	3	4
2	Tandale	1	2	3	4
3	Masasani	2	1	6	2
4	Sinza	2	1	6	2
5	Mbezi	1	2	2	4
Sub-Total		7	9	20	16
Grand- Total		16		36	

Data Collection Techniques

Data collection for this study utilised qualitative methods, including in-depth interviews, direct observations, focus group discussions (FGDs), and documentary analysis.

In-depth Interviews

In-depth interviews were conducted with the study participants, the key informants from the selected private companies, the formal groups, and wards’ representatives. A total of 41 interviews were conducted (20 from private companies, 16 from informal groups, and 5 from Ward Executive Officers), with each interview lasting approximately not more than thirty minutes. Interviews were semi-structured, allowing for flexibility to explore emerging themes and perspectives.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

Focus group discussions included members of private companies and informal groups to gain insights into challenges associated with waste sorting, reuse, and recovery in the contracted localities. A total of two FGDs were conducted (one for private companies and the other for informal groups, with each group comprising six participants. FGDs provided a forum for group interaction, shared experiences and perspectives.

Direct Observations

The researcher conducted direct observations to observe waste management practices within the study area. The observations were at the waste collection points, recycling centres, and other relevant locations. Detailed field notes were taken during observations to document key findings and observations.

Documentary Analysis

Documentary analysis involved the review of relevant documents, including government reports, policy documents, and organisational records related to solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City. Documents were reviewed, and sourced from Wards offices (reports, SWM regulations, SWM contracts), internet sources (SWM policy), private companies and informal groups' offices (reports).

Research Instruments

To facilitate data collection, the tools utilised included Unstructured Interview Guides to guide in-depth interviews, providing a framework for exploring key topics while allowing flexibility to probe into emerging themes. The field researcher used notebooks to record detailed field notes during direct observations, documenting observations, insights, and reflections in real-time. In addition, a Mobile Phone Recorder was utilised to record audio during interviews and focus group discussions, ensuring accurate capturing of participant responses and discussions.

Data Analysis

Qualitative content analysis was employed to analyse the collected qualitative data. Data analysis occurred concurrently with data collection, involving processes more or less as described by Zhang and Wildemuth (2009) which includes transcribing recorded data, reading interview responses multiple times, data coding, category generation, and data grouping to streamline categories concerning research questions. The researcher then organised the data into a textual display, facilitating linkage of data to research questions and subsequent discussion. For clarity of phrases like "most," "majority," and "few," simple descriptive statistics (quasi-statistics) in terms of percentages were utilised.

Data Credibility

Data credibility was ensured through the triangulation of multiple data collection methods, including interviews, observations, focus group discussions, and documentary analysis. Triangulation enhances the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings by corroborating information from different sources and perspectives. In addition, thick descriptions and direct quotations are used to contextualise findings, providing transparency and enabling readers to assess the credibility of the study's conclusions.

Findings and Discussion

Challenges Private Stakeholders Face in Attaining Sustainable Solid Waste Management

The following section presents the findings and discussion about the first specific objective of this study: challenges the private sector encounters in managing solid waste sustainably in Dar es Salaam City. Through a comprehensive examination of the data collected from in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, direct observations, and documentary analysis, this section sheds light on the key obstacles faced by private companies and informal groups engaged in waste management initiatives. The findings of the study revealed several themes which reflect the challenges that both private companies and informal groups face as follows;

Decision-Making Challenges

In examining challenges in sustainable solid waste management (SWM) in Dar es Salaam City, the participants in in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were asked to narrate any challenges they experienced when managing solid waste, particularly, in an attempt to separate waste materials, reuse, recycling and recovery. Findings revealed a significant deficiency in stakeholder engagement in decision-making processes, with two (2) companies and three (3) informal groups unable to participate in decision-making processes for more than a year since January 2023 due to improper communication channels on meeting schedules, often they become unaware of the scheduled meetings where most of the decisions regarding SWM activities are discussed and clarified. On the side of the contracting local government authorities, they claim to send invitations through calls and text messages, moreover, they believe participation in the meetings depends on the willingness of the company itself.

This finding implies that the decision-making process on SWM is not well organised to ensure the participation of all stakeholders particularly in the private sector. Although the members of the private sector who are not participating in decision-making are seemingly few (5 or 31.25%), their participation is essential for reaching effective SWM decisions. Participating in decision-making by the private sector in Dar es Salaam City is important due to the socio-economic and cultural dynamics of the city in terms of its high population and being a commercial hub of the country, it presents unique challenges and strategies for waste management.

The poor participation of the private sector in decision-making has made the contracting authorities continue focusing on SW collection and transportation to the dump site. A similar situation is reported by Jacob, Kris, and Mengiseny (2021), Dar es Salaam City focuses on transporting the collected waste to the dumpsite despite having a high potential for recycling. The effective participation of the private sector, who are also the community members in the decision-making process is essential in facilitating relevant measures for promoting sorting, reuse and recycling practices in the city. Likewise, Dangi and Jamal (2016) highlight the importance of participatory approaches in waste management decision-making.

In terms of the power dynamics, the study revealed that the passive role assumed by the private sector in decision-making processes reflects an imbalance of power, hindering the development of innovative SWM solutions in Dar es Salaam City. Considerably, 4 private companies and 5 informal groups (approximately 82%) of the private entities that participated in decision-making said they played a passive role by listening and receiving instructions; one of the private company representatives expressed, "*We are often left out when it comes to discussing the broader aspects of waste management, and we end up just following orders*".

The finding highlights passive participation in decision-making limits sustainable practices of SWM. This is because, the decisions reached lack essential discussions on strategies to harness solid waste as a valuable resource through separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery. Therefore, it is important to harness power imbalances by allowing the active participation of private sector representatives in decision-making processes. The same is observed by Ismaila et al. (2022), who emphasise the need to address power imbalances in SWM initiatives.

Moreover, the findings on the predominant focus of the decision-making on logistical concerns particularly of collection and transportation rather than on SW separation/sorting, reuse, recycling and recovery, make the approaches fail to adequately address the scale of waste generation and management practices, posing additional challenges to sustainable SWM. According to the participation theory by Reed, et al. (2017), there is a need for an inclusive engagement that integrates stakeholders' interests for informed and effective decision-making. A similar observation is made by Ismaila, et al. (2022) that informal waste pickers play important roles in SW reuse and recycling and, thus, should be integrated into SWM decision-making processes. This implies that collaborative efforts between government organs and the private sector both formal (private companies) and informal entities (informal groups) may foster a decision-making framework which is adequate in accommodating the multifaceted requirements of sustainable SWM.

Limited Emphasis on SW Sorting, Reuse, Recycling and Recovery Practices

In conjunction with the challenges stemming from ineffective participation in decision-making, this study discloses a noticeable absence of emphasis on sustainable solid waste management (SWM) practices among local government authorities in Dar es Salaam City. The sustainable practices focused in this study include SW separation or sorting, reuse, recycling and recovery, however, through the analysis of SWM contracts obtained from the five wards selected, the study reveals a disconnect between engagement strategies and these sustainable SWM practices.

Likewise, the local authorities prioritise SW collection and transportation as reported by all the sixteen private sector entities, as said by one of the representatives of an informal group, "*We focus more on collecting and transporting waste to the dumpsite because that's what we are paid for, even the Ward Office is not concerned about separation, reuse and recovery*" This oversight undermines the potential for positive environmental outcomes, as highlighted by Kihila, Wernsted, and Kaseva (2021), who stress the pivotal role of waste segregation in facilitating reuse and recycling; as they have

a great impact on reducing the valuable waste materials that would otherwise end up being disposed of. Recycling, in particular, holds the potential to significantly reduce the volume of waste needing disposal, thereby reducing transportation costs, extending the lifespan of sanitary landfills, and mitigating environmental and health risks (Khandelwal, Dhar, Thalla, & Kumar, 2019).

The exclusive focus on collection and transportation suggests a lack of inclusivity and transparency in decision-making processes, hindering informed decision-making and positive environmental outcomes. This finding contradicts the design element of participation theory that emphasises transparent and inclusive engagement to represent stakeholders' interests. In line with this finding, Ismaila et al. (2022) emphasise the need for more collaborative approaches to unlock sustainable SWM solutions.

The study's findings further show that the limited priority given to separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery practices can be partially attributed to insufficient knowledge about these techniques. This was reported by most participants from the informal groups in the focus group discussion, findings show that even though they attempted to separate valuable recyclable materials informally they did not have a good knowledge about it and did not have any training access from the contracting authorities. This finding implies that the informal groups contracted to provide SWM services in Dar es Salaam City lack the necessary skills for sorting, recycling and recovering valuable SW materials.

The finding aligns with the arguments by Godfrey (2021) that waste management in developing nations often operates with inadequate knowledge of waste handling. It was also observed by Kumar, et al. (2017) and Rai and Goswami (2019) that several challenges associated with SWM are connected to the limited availability of qualified waste management professionals. All these findings underscore the need for a shift towards more sustainable SWM strategies through collaborating with experts and investing in education to harness the untapped potential of waste as a resource.

Generally, the study's finding on limited emphasis towards sustainable SWM practices exposes a critical issue within Dar es Salaam City's local government, where SWM primarily revolves around collection and transportation, often overlooking practices like sorting or segregation, recycling, and recovery. Unfortunately, the significance of sustainable SWM practices frequently goes unnoticed and are informally practised in Dar es Salaam City. This finding signifies inefficiency and a missed opportunity to transform waste into valuable raw materials.

Inefficiencies in Solid Waste Management Contracts

In exploring the contractual frameworks governing solid waste management (SWM) in Dar es Salaam City, this study sheds light on inefficiencies that hamper the progression of sustainable SWM practices. Findings reveal a narrow scope within contracts issued by local authorities at the ward level, primarily focusing on waste collection and transportation to designated disposal sites (Pugu Kinyerezi). The inefficiencies of the contracts were reported by all seven private companies and nine informal groups interviewed, as well as in all the two focused group discussion sections. One representative from a private waste collection company said; *"The contract is quite*

restrictive. It focuses on collection and disposal, as it doesn't mention recycling or waste recovery." Similarly, the researcher observed SWM practices by all the private companies and the informal groups were predominantly collection and transportation of SW to the dump site.

This revelation suggests that contracts confine the scope of SWM activities to collection and transportation to the dumpsite resulting in the exclusion of essential practices such as waste separation and recycling. These findings further imply a failure to take up the opportunity for utilising SW because Dar es Salaam is a commercial hub of the country reflecting possibilities of commercialising SW for manufacturing and industrial production as reusable, recyclable, and recoverable materials rather than extracting new raw materials. Consequently, informal groups, individuals, and private investors take on these tasks outside the contractual framework. This highlights a significant inadequacy where contracts fail to address the comprehensive requirements of sustainable waste management, emphasising the urgency for contractual reform within the private sector engagement model. Currently, contracts maintain a narrow-minded focus on collection and transportation, neglecting the overarching goal of achieving sustainable SWM.

While there is limited literature on SWM contract issues, this finding aligns with observations made by Yoda, Chirawurah, and Adongo (2014) in Accra, Ghana, where contracted agents primarily deal with waste transfer to disposal centres. Similarly, arguments presented by Kirama and Mayo (2016), Sarfo-Mensah, Obeng-Okrah, and Arhin (2019), and Nyampundu, Mwegoha, and Millanzi (2020) regarding the predominant role of private companies in SW collection and transportation imply the inadequacy of existing contracts in supporting sustainable SWM practices. An important concern which is also relevant to the findings of this study is given by Mohammed and van Dijk (2017) that there is a need to entrust private companies with meaningful and sustainable involvement in SWC by associating contracts with conditions concerning sustainability.

Additionally, the study findings reveal that all contracts issued to all the sixteen private entities participating in SWM in Dar es Salaam City are limited to one-year and two-year renewable terms. The implication of this finding on the design lens of the participatory theory means the prevalence of short-term contracts further hampers the private sector's ability to invest in the technology and infrastructure required for effective waste management. Due to short-term contracts, the two parties do not yield sustainable results in utilising SW resources despite their collaborations.

While the findings of this study indicate short-term contracts affect the sustainability of SWM, the study findings by Spoann, Fujiwara, Seng, Lay, and Yim (2019) revealed that the long-term contract design attempts for partnerships may result in a worsening of the situation by facilitating new ways of concentration, inefficiency and political interest. This contracting finding implies that sustainable SWM contract durations should be adjusted based on the long-term nature of SWM improvements without undermining the socio-economic context of a specific locality where a service is provided.

In summary, the findings from the first specific objective highlight key challenges in achieving sustainable solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City. These challenges encompass ineffective decision-making processes, limited emphasis on sustainable SWM practices by local government authorities, and inefficiencies in solid waste management contracts. To address these issues and advance sustainable SWM, it is essential to promote inclusive decision-making, increase awareness of sustainable practices, and reform SWM contracts to align with long-term sustainability goals. In addition, while participation theory offers valuable insights into stakeholder engagement and decision-making processes, it has not fully considered the complexities and limitations inherent in contractual agreements. Therefore, although the theory provides a relevant framework for analysing stakeholder engagement, its applicability to contractual dynamics within SWM in Dar es Salaam City may require refinement of theoretical perspectives.

Opportunities Available for Attaining Sustainable Solid Waste Management Through Private Sector Engagement

The second specific objective focused on exploring the opportunities that arise by contracting the private sector to promote sustainable waste management including sorting or separation, reuse, recycling and recovery in Dar es Salaam City. Building upon the challenges identified in the first specific objective, these findings extract a range of opportunities for utilising the private sector's potential to enhance sustainable waste management. The findings of the study revealed the following themes which uncover the available opportunities;

Harnessing Private Sector Technology

The findings in this study uncover the available opportunity for advancing sustainable solid waste management (SWM) by tapping into cutting-edge private sector technologies. Notably, three out of seven (approx. 43%) of the interviewed private companies are eager to tap into the untapped potential residing in collected waste through recycling and transforming waste into new products, envisioning waste not as a burden but as a resource that can generate additional income. This dual focus on sustainability and economic empowerment revealed by the contracted private companies is a noteworthy development. One of the private company representatives said *“If we can be contracted for recycling SW or undertaking energy recovery at the dumpsite, we are willing to import technology for that purpose”*

This dual focus on sustainability and economic empowerment aligns with the contextual understanding of the private sector SWM service providers in Dar es Salaam City, although to a limited extent since less than half (approx. 43%) revealed a desire to invest in SW recycling and recovery. Furthermore, the finding reflects a design element, emphasising the significance of a transparent and inclusive contract for innovative solutions beyond traditional waste collection and transportation. The eagerness of private companies to invest in technology for sustainable SWM practices aligns with the power element, implying the potential of collaborative approaches between public and private sectors in shaping waste management strategies.

The finding implies an opportunity for improving traditional SWM that focuses on collection, transportation and disposal and turns into sorting, reuse, recycling and recovery using modern technologies. This improvement is possible since some private companies are willing to import waste recycling and technologies. This finding supports that of Albostan and Sharifli (2023) who observed that the private sector in Global South Countries led to the use of mobile application technology called Gringgo which enables users to photograph waste items which are then identified using image recognition technology for determining their market value. In turn, this technology has helped to reduce waste quantities. Likewise, Kosoe, Diawuo, and Osumanu (2019) argued that the benefits of involving the private sector in SWM should be examined for its technological contribution.

From this finding, it is crucial to acknowledge the stumbling blocks that accompany the vision of technological improvement for SW recycling and recovery in Dar es Salaam City it is due to the contractual necessity to transport all the collected waste to the central dumpsite. The insights from a ward executive officer, a key informant in this study revealed the same he said: *“At the Ward Level we are only contracting private companies and informal groups to collect waste and transport it to the dumpsite, we can redirect efforts to waste recycling if we see modelling practices from the Waste Department of the City Council”*. This means contracted private companies tend to shy away from investments in recycling and recovery technologies due to contractual constraints.

Generally, the findings of this study on harnessing private sector technology reflect the need for a comprehensive approach that fosters inclusive and transparent contract design, rebalances power dynamics and aligns contract durations with the long-term nature of technological investments.

Forging Links between Solid Waste Management and Other Economic Sectors

This study reveals the opportunity for advancing sustainable solid waste management (SWM) by fostering connections between SWM entities and other economic sectors. The study probed the existence of formal or informal horizontal links between private companies or informal groups engaged in waste collection and various sectors, particularly in the industrial domain. Horizontal links, in this context, refer to collaborative relationships between SWM entities and other economic sectors, where resources and expertise are shared to enhance waste management practices.

The findings of this study revealed the presence of emerging connections, even though limited and informal, between a limited number of private companies (two out of seven) and informal groups (four out of nine) and recycling centres. This finding implies restricted emerging links between private SWM service providers and economic sectors, particularly, the manufacturing sector. This finding is similar to that observed in European Union Countries by Tomić and Schneider (2020) that the link between waste generation and economic indicators is still weak.

Despite being limited and informal, the emerging ties in Dar es Salaam City involve the supply of waste materials for recycling and recovery purposes, thereby enabling the utilisation of waste resources that would otherwise be transferred to disposal. One of the

private company representatives said, *"We have started collaborating with some of the local recycling centres to give them some of the plastic waste that we collect which is sorted by our casual workers. It's a win-win situation – they get the raw materials they need, and we reduce the waste we send to the dumpsite, and sometimes our casual workers get some money."*

The study findings further revealed the government authorities at the ward levels are aware of the existing informal links between the informal groups or the private companies and the recycling centres. This was revealed by most of the Ward Executive Officers during one-to-one in-depth interview sessions as one of them said: "There are some of the informal groups that supply recyclable waste materials to the nearby recycling centres, this kind of collaboration is an excellent initiative that we should encourage". This finding implies waste separation and recycling should be promoted more in Dar es Salaam, as it is limited and informally conducted.

This finding aligns with Schübeler, Christen, and Wehrle (1996) who emphasised that horizontal links require support from community members involved in various sectors, including manufacturing and industrial centres, to strengthen sustainable SWM efforts. Such inter-sectoral connections promote the integration of sustainable elements within the waste management paradigm. Similarly, Ellen (2011) emphasised that in low- and middle-income countries recycling should be viewed as a private economic activity with strong direct links to the industrial sector.

The implications of these findings suggest that the formalisation of horizontal links between SWM and other economic sectors within waste management contracts can pave the way for enhanced sustainability practices. This proposition is encouraged by Schübeler, Christen, and Wehrle's (1996) call for clarifying relationships and linkages between municipal SWM and other municipal service sectors within the urban management framework. Thus, in Dar es Salaam City, there are opportunities for establishing connections between contracted private companies/groups with the economic agencies that can utilise SW resources in production; this needs to be formalised and promoted to enhance SWM sustainability.

Generally, this finding underscores the potential for advancing sustainable solid waste management (SWM) in Dar es Salaam City by fostering horizontal links between SWM entities and other economic sectors. The informal nature of these ties highlights the need for inclusive and transparent design in contractual arrangements to formalise and promote such connections. By officially acknowledging and supporting these connections, there is an opportunity to rebalance power dynamics and foster a more democratic approach to waste management decision-making. Furthermore, this aligns with the participatory approach advocated by participation theory, emphasising the importance of inclusive engagement and collaborative strategy among stakeholders.

Generally, the mind map of the study findings includes the identified challenges that focus on logistical restrictions, contractual constraints, capacity issues, and financial constraints. The opportunities lie in the utilization of the private sector's willingness to promote technological investment in waste reuse, recycling and recovery. Another opportunity is the ability of the private sector to develop horizontal links which can

facilitate economic integration with other sectors for using waste resources and increasing government awareness on sustainable SWM practices

Limitations of the Study

This study faced several limitations that need to be acknowledged. The research is geographically confined to Dar es Salaam, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions with different socio-economic and cultural contexts. The qualitative nature of the study, relying on interviews, focus group discussions, and observations, limits the quantification of issues. Moreover, the focus on private sector stakeholders and local government authorities may overlook the perspectives of other actors such as waste pickers, community members, and environmental NGOs. Despite these limitations, the study provides a wide-ranging understanding of the challenges and opportunities in SWM, providing critical areas for policy intervention and the potential for enhancing sustainable practices through private sector engagement.

Conclusion, Policy Implication, Areas for Further Studies

This study has explored a complex landscape of sustainable solid waste management (SWM) in Dar es Salaam City. Findings regarding challenges the contracted private sector faces underscore the need for an inclusive decision-making process that encompasses logistical aspects and strategies for waste separation, recycling, and recovery. Moreover, opportunities identified for the private sector's engagement revealed promising opportunities for advancing SWM through acknowledging and formalising the emerging informal horizontal links between solid waste management agencies and other economic sectors. This finding is similar to the arguments by Ismaila et al. (2022) who emphasised the need for more collaborative approaches to unlock sustainable SWM solutions. These findings highlight the importance of collaborative approaches and transparent design in enhancing waste management practices. By integrating participation theory principles into waste management policies and practices, there is potential for achieving more effective and sustainable SWM outcomes in Dar es Salaam City, ultimately contributing to positive environmental and social impacts.

According to the study conclusion, based on the findings on contractual limitations on traditional SWM practices, this study recommends that policymakers should offer specific roles for governmental and non-governmental players on SW separated at source, reuse, recycling, and recovery, according to the study's conclusions. Municipal waste management agencies should evaluate SWM policies and bylaws to strengthen source-based SW separation, reuse, recycling, and recovery methods. Moreover, based on the findings of the available opportunities to promote technological innovation in waste management, the Municipal Solid Waste Management Departments, Wards' Environmental Management Committees and private stakeholders should examine SWM contracts to enable the private sector to recycle, recover, and deliver recyclable SW materials to manufacturing facilities/industries.

While this study provides awareness of the challenges and opportunities of sustainable solid waste management (SWM) by the contracted private sector in Dar es Salaam City,

future research could focus on comparative studies across multiple cities or regions to explore contextual factors influencing SWM practices.

References

- Singh, S. G. (2021). Tanzania: An assessment of the solid waste-management ecosystem. New Delhi: Centre for Science and Environment.
- (URT), U. R. (2023). President's Office Regional Administration and Local Government Dar es Salaam City Council. Dar es Salaam: Dar es Salaam City Council. Retrieved January 2024, from President's Office Regional Administration and Local Government
- Abubakar, I. R., Maniruzzaman, K. M., Dano, U. L., AlShihri, F. S., AlShammari, M. S., Ahmed, S. S., & Alrawaf, T. I. (2022). Environmental sustainability impacts of solid waste management practices in the global South. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19 (19).
- Afful, B. B., Addaney , M., Anaifo, D., Akudugu , J. A., Borkor , F. K., Yeboah, E. O., & Sampana, J. (2023). Public-private partnership in municipal solid waste management in the Sunyani municipality of Ghana. *Journal of Property, Planning and Environmental Law*.
- Albostan, A., & Sharifli, Y. (2023). Case studies: the role of the private sector Harnessing the role of the private sector in waste. Istanbul: UNDP.
- Ansari, A., Dharm Dutt, D., & Vivek, K. (2024). Catalysing paradigm shifts in global waste Management: A case study of Saharanpur Smart city. *Waste Management Bulletin*, 2(1), 29-38.
- Dangi, T. B., & Jamal, T. (2016). An Integrated Approach to “Sustainable Community-Based Tourism. *Sustainability*, 475.
- Darmey, J., Ahiekpor , J. C., Narra, S., & Achaw, O. (2023). Municipal Solid Waste Generation Trend and Bioenergy Recovery Potential: A Review. *Energies*, 16(23), 7753.
- David, A., Thangavel, Y. D., & Sankriti, R. (2019). Recover, recycle and reuse: An efficient way to reduce the waste. *Environmental Challenges*, 31-42.
- De, F. G., Ferrara, C., Iannone, V., & Parente, P. (2019). Improving the efficacy of municipal solid waste collection with a communicative approach based on easily understandable indicators. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2380-2390.
- Ellen, G. (2011). Recovering resources, creating opportunities: Integrating the informal sector into solid waste management. Eschborn: Aksoy Print, Eppelheim.

- Farrah, L., & Ng'ang'a, P. (2022). Effectiveness of stakeholders involvement and solid waste management in Mombasa County Kenya. *International Academic Journal of Economics and Finance*, 3(7), 127-142.
- Gelan, E. (2021). Municipal Solid Waste Management Practices for Achieving Green Architecture Concepts in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Technologies* 9(3), 48.
- Godfrey, L. (2021). *Waste management practices in developing countries*. Basel: MDPI-Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute.
- Ighravwea, D. E., & Edemb, I. E. (2020). Municipal waste management sustainability in developing countries: An analysis of research directions. *The Journal of Solid Waste Technology and Management*, 46(3), 328-341.
- Ismaila, R. A., Khandoker, M. M., Umar, L. D., Faez, S. A., Maher, S. A., Sayed, M. A., . . . Tareq, I. A. (2022). Environmental Sustainability Impacts of Solid Waste Management Practices in the Global South. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12717.
- Jacob, K. M., Kris, W., & Mengiseny, K. E. (2021). Waste segregation and potential for recycling -A case study in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Sustainable Environment*, 1935532.
- Kamugisha , P., Ludete , J., & Mhanga, S. (2019). Public-private partnerships for successful solid waste management and prospects for reducing public health risks in Kinondoni Municipality-Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Environmental Research and Technology*, 2(3), 141-157.
- Khandelwal , H., Dhar, H., Thalla, A. K., & Kumar, S. (2019). Application of life cycle assessment in municipal solid waste management: A worldwide critical review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 209, 630-654.
- Kihila, J. M., Wernsted, K., & Kaseva, M. (2021). Waste segregation and potential for a recycling case study in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Sustainable Environment*, 7(1), 1935532.
- Kihila, J. M., Wernsted, K., & Kaseva, M. (2021). Waste segregation and potential for a recycling case study in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Sustainable Environment*, 7(1), 1935532.
- Kirama, A., & Mayo, A. W. (2016). Challenges and prospects of private sector participation in solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Habitat International*, 53, 195-205.
- Kirama, A., & Mayo, A. W. (2016). Challenges and prospects of private sector participation in solid waste management in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. *Habitat International*, 53, 195-205.

- Koiwanit, J., & Filimonau, V. (2023). Stakeholder collaboration for solid waste management in a small tourism island. *PLoS one*, 18(7), e0288839.
- Kosoe, E. A., Diawuo, F., & Osumanu, I. K. (2019). Looking into the past: Rethinking traditional ways of solid waste management in the Jaman South Municipality, Ghana. *Ghana Journal of Geography*, 11(1), 228-244.
- Kumar, S., Smith, S. R., Fowler, G., Velis, C., Kumar, S., & Arya, S. (2017). Challenges and opportunities associated with waste management in India. *Royal Society Open Science*, 4(3), 160764.
- Mapunda, A. S., Joseph, K. R., & Kasuwi, S. (2023). Impact of Population Dynamics on Solid Waste Generation Trends in Dar Es Salaam Metropolitan. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 6(1), 75-87.
- Mapunda, A. S., Joseph, K. R., & Kasuwi, S. (2023). Impact of Population Dynamics on Solid Waste Generation Trends in Dar Es Salaam Metropolitan. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 6(1), 75-87.
- Mapunda, S. A., Kimwaga, J. R., & Kasuwi, S. (2023). Impact of Population Dynamics on Solid Waste Generation Trends in Dar Es Salaam Metropolitan. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 6(1), 75-87.
- Mhache, E. P. (2012). Dar es Salaam City and Challenges in Solid Waste Management. The Case of Manzese and Sinza Wards in Dar es Salaam. *Huria: Journal of the Open University of Tanzania*, 10(1), 78-91.
- Mnguu, B. Y., & Eliamani, S. (2021). Assessment of the outsourced strategies for on solid waste management services in the city of Dodoma. The 2nd East African Conference of Business Management, Arusha- Tanzania. Dodoma: Institute of Accountancy, Arusha.
- Mohammed, A. A., & van Dijk, P. M. (2017). Practice and determinants of solid waste collection: the case of private collectors in five Ethiopian Cities. *Int J Waste Resour*, 7(280), 2.
- Mushi, G. J., Banele, S. D., & Mollel, A. B. (2022). Income and Value Chain Activities in Informal Solid Waste Collection in Tandale, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 92-100.
- Muturi, E. (2021). Influence of stakeholders' participation and management of solid waste disposal. A critical literature review. *Journal of Environment Vol.1, Issue No. 1*, 14- 29.
- Muyiwa, L. A., Ridwan, T., & Hans-Rudolf, B. (2023). Municipal Solid Waste Collection and Coverage Rates in Sub-Saharan African Countries: A Comprehensive Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Waste (Vol. 1, No. 2)*, 389-413.

- United Nations. (NA). Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development. Retrieved from <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org>.
- Nayono, S., & Nayono, S. E. (2021). Mapping the Problems, Stakeholders, and Potential Solutions of Solid Waste Management in a New-Emergence Tourist Area: A Case Study in Nglanggeran, Gunungsewu UNESCO Global Geopark. *Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 832, No. 1, 012066).
- Nyampundu , K., Mwegoha , W. J., & Millanzi, W. C. (2020). Sustainable solid waste management Measures in Tanzania: An exploratory descriptive case study among vendors at Majengo market in Dodoma City. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1-16.
- Perkumienè, D., Atalay, A., Safaa, L., & Grigienè, J. (2023). Sustainable waste management for clean and safe environments in the recreation and tourism sector: a case study of Lithuania, Turkey and Morocco. *Recycling* 8(4), 56.
- Prince , N. K., Ted , Y. A., & Dzidzo , Y.-T. (2020). Stakeholder Participation for Sustainable Solid Waste Management. *American Journal of Environment Studies*, 44- 60.
- Priya, A. (2021). Case study methodology of qualitative research: Key attributes and navigating the conundrums in its application. *Sociological Bulletin*, 70(1), 94-110.
- Rai, B., & Goswami, S. (2019). Urbanisation and tourism induced challenges in waste management in hill towns: a case of Gangtok. *Waste Management and Resource Efficiency: Proceedings of 6th IconSWM 2016* (pp. 393-407). Singapore: Springer.
- Reed, M., Vella, S., Challies, E., de Vente, J., Frewer, L., Hohenwallner-Ries, D., . . . van Delden, H. (2017). A theory of participation: What makes stakeholder and public engagement in environmental management work? *A journal of Society for Economical Restoration*. 26, S7-s17.
- Saleh , M., & Marzuki, A. (2023). challenges of SWM Hierarchy System: The Stakeholders New Saga in Perspectives. In Z. Suhaiza, & S. Suriyanarayanan, *Solid Waste and Landfills Management-Recent Advances*. IntechOpen.
- Sarfo-Mensah , P., Obeng-Okrah , K., & Arhin, A. A. (2019). Solid waste management in urban communities in Ghana: A case study of the Kumasi metropolis. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 13(9), 342-353.
- Schübeler, P., Christen, J., & Wehrle, K. (1996). Conceptual framework for municipal solid waste management in low-income countries. Nairobi: Swiss Centre for Development Cooperation.
- Spoann, V., Fujiwara, T., Seng, B., Lay, C., & Yim, M. (2019). Assessment of public-private partnership in municipal solid waste management in Phnom Penh, Cambodia. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1228.

- Tomić, T., & Schneider, D. R. (2020). Circular economy in waste management–Socio-economic effect of changes in waste management system structure. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 267, 110564.
- United Nations. (2008). *Global and regional developments on issues related to principle 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development*. Riga: Economic and Social Council.
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT). (2018). *The national solid waste management strategy*. Dar es Salaam: Hekima na Uhuru.
- University of Dar es Salaam. (2020). *Assessment of challenges associated with solid waste disposal management and proposed solutions*. Dar es Salaam.
- Wang, E., Changhong, M., & Xiaofei, C. (2022). Circular economy and the changing geography of international trade in plastic waste. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15020.
- Yoda, R. M., Chirawurah, D., & Adongo, P. B. (2014). Domestic waste disposal practice and perceptions of private sector waste management in urban Accra. *BMC Public Health*, 14(1), 1-10.
- Zhang, Y., & Wildemuth, B. M. (2009). Qualitative analysis of content Applications of Social Research Methods to Questions. *Information and Library Science*.

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